

Studies of morphometric characteristics of *Cirrhinus mrigala* at Chashma Lake, Mianwali, Pakistan

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SUMMARY

This research was carried to examine the growth and health of *Cirrhinus mrigala* individuals from Chashma Lake in Mianwali, Pakistan. Throughout the research duration, a total of 40 fish specimens were collected for morphometric analysis. The results demonstrated a logarithmic association between total body weight and length in *C. mrigala*. Regressions with coefficients of determination ($r^2=0.984115$) were strong important ($r=0.992026$). The output value for the association of logarithmic between standard length (SL) and total length ($b=1.017$) was found to be extremely near to one, indicating that *C. mrigala* has isometric development among TL as well as SL. The range difference was utilized to define the environmentally regulated, intermediate, and genetically controlled characteristics after establishing a relationship between the morphometric and total lengths. According to the findings of the study, Chashma Lake in Mianwali, Pakistan, has a better hydrological regime and is less ecologically deteriorated, offering favorable circumstances for fishing.

Keyword: *Cirrhinus mrigala*, Morphometric characters, Growth

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INTRODUCTION

Fish are significant in the kingdom 'Animalia' because they provide crucial nutrients to their ecology and assist manage the food web. Several industrialized and developing nations have seen significant expansion in the aquaculture sectors during the last few decades (Hilton and Taylor, 2000). In 2010, the yearly catch in wild and aquaculture was 149 million tonnes (IUCN, 2012). Fish accounts for around 17% of world protein consumption (FAO, 2014). For the fiscal year 2003-2004, Pakistan exported around 104937 tonnes of fish valued at 156254 million US\$ by FAO (2015). Aquaculture sector of Pakistan added 232.5 million US\$ to the country's GDP according to FAO (2008). The fish productivity cannot be assessed without first identifying the variety of the river, lacking, or ponds. The diversity of the fish community and morphology demonstrates the effect of environmental conditions on the river ecology (Taylor *et al.*, 2006). The measurement of fish diversity aids in identifying the presence of fish species, whereas morphometric properties of fish aid

in understanding fish development so that someone is aware of the growing problem of fish in the water body.

The investigation of fish length-weight relationships was counted as essential factors for the estimation of production, biomass of fish populations, survival rate of fish, growth rate of fish, maturity rate of fish, reproduction, conservation, stock assessment, and it compares the history of life between the fish of different regions and fish populations with general wellbeing (LeCren, 1951; Bayhan, 2008). Fish from all over the world, like all other animals, suffer from parasitic infections that slow down their growth, with daily losses estimated at 2 to 3 g per day at stocking densities greater than 12000. The shape and biology of fishes vary greatly depending on the environments they inhabit (Froese and Pauly, 1988). Fishes were ranked as the most diversified group of main vertebrates (Magurran, 2004; Altaf *et al.*, 2013).

Numerous research on fish diversity have been carried out on various water bodies to examine fish fauna in all provinces of Pakistan by Mirza, 1994; George, 1995; Rafique and Qureshi, 1997; Rafique, 2003; Mirza and Sharif, 2003; Rafique *et al.*, 2007; Khan *et al.*, 2011; Rafique *et al.*, 2012; Hussain *et al.*, 2016. A total of 27,977 fish species from 62 orders and 515 families were investigated worldwide (Nelson, 2006; Helfman *et al.*, 2009). A total of 8,000 freshwater fishes have been reported worldwide, with 186 freshwater species found in Pakistan. Thirty fish species out of 186 were commercially significant (Peter, 1999). 179 freshwater fish species were identified (Mirza *et al.*, 1999; Mirza, 2004). Rafique *et al.* (2012) reported 193 fish species from Pakistan's freshwater bodies in their study.

The research of the length-weight association of fishes in aquaculture has numerous applications, including the estimation of fish production, biomass, rate of fish survival, rate of fish growth, rate of maturity of fish, reproduction, conservation, stock assessment, and comparing the life history of fish between various regions at the genus and population numbers, as well as the overall health of fish (LeCren, 1951). Contaminated water releases toxic, heavy metals, oils, hydrocarbons, radioactive substances, pesticides, herbicides, fungicides, non-biodegradable products, and various toxic materials like acid and bases, which have a negative impact on the morphology, physiology, metabolism, and improvement of fishes by affecting their organs such as intestine, liver, gills, eyes, and skins disrupting the normal physiology of all (Rafique *et al.*, 2013; Sharma *et al.*, 2014). Studies show that polyculture technique in the fish farming is the main cause of fish diseases because pathogen can transfer directly or indirectly from one host to another host (Iqbal *et al.*, 2001; Altaf *et al.*, 2008). The main objectives of the research were to observe the morphometric characters of four carp fishes at Chashma reservoir.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

DESCRIPTION OF AREA

Chashma Lake is located on the Indus River which is critically important for 160 million peoples of Pakistan, and irrigates 80% of the agricultural land of Pakistan, that covered an area of 21.5 million hectares of agricultural land (Scott, 1989; Mirza, 2014; Altaf *et al.*, 2014). The flood level of “Chashma Barrage” is maximum “37 ft”. The area is of 60 feet wide. Chashma Lake is known to be an important wetland

(IUCN, 1989; Gorham and Janssens, 1992; Altaf *et al.*, 2014). A large number of fishes, birds, reptiles, and herptiles are also found at this place (Rafique, 2005; Mirza, 2006; Ahmad *et al.*, 2016).

Figure 1: Chashma Reservoir Satellite Picture.

METHODOLOGY FOR FISH MORPHOMETRY

A total 40 specimens of *Cirrhinus mrigala* were collected from Chashma Lake, District Mianwali, Punjab, Pakistan. The fish specimens were preserved in the box having ice in them and transferred to laboratory of UOL Sargodha Campus. During study the specimens observed with abnormal or broken tails were rejected. The following morphometric parameters were noted.

Body Weight (W)

The body weight of fish was measured on digital scale (SF-400) having weight bearing capacity up to 7 Kg. The weight of the fish was measured in grams.

Total Length (TL)

The total fish length was taken from the fish snout to the last tip of caudal fin or tail.

Standard Length

Standard length was taken from the tip of fish snout to the end of the flesh part of the body.

Head Length (HL)

The head length of the fish was taken from the most anterior part of the snout to the posterior edge of opercular bone above the gills. Metal scale was used fitted on wooden board for the measurement of TL, SL and HL of the fish.

Body Girth BG

Body girth was measured with plastic fiber tap by applying it perpendicular to the length taken from the widest part of the fish.

Dorsal Fin Length Measurement (DFL)

The dorsal fin length was taken from fin base to longest ray of the fin.

Dorsal Fin Base Measurement (DFB)

Dorsal fin base was taken from fin flesh base that was attached with body.

Pelvic Fin Length Measurement (PvFL)

Pelvic fin length was taken from the base to the longest ray of the fin.

Pelvic Fin Base Measurement (PvFB)

Pelvic fin base measurement was taken at fin flesh base that was attached with body.

Pectoral Fin Length Measurement (PtFL)

Pectoral fin length measurement was taken at pectoral fin flesh base that was attached with body to the longest ray of the pectoral fin.

Pectoral Fin Base Measurement (PtFB)

Pectoral fin base measurement was taken at pectoral fin flesh base that was attached with body.

Anal Fin Length Measurement (AFL)

Anal fin length measurement was taken at anal fin flesh base that was attached with body to the longest ray of the anal fin.

Anal Fin Base Measurement (AFB)

Anal fin base measurement was taken at the anal fin flesh base that was attached with the fish body.

Caudal Fin Length Measurement (CFL)

Caudal fin length measurement was taken at the caudal fin flesh base that was attached with body flesh to the longest ray of the caudal fin.

Caudal Fin width measurement (CFW)

Caudal fin width measurement was taken at the base of the caudal fin flesh that was attached with the fish body. All fin length and fin base measurements were taken with the help of vernier caliper having least count less than 0.001.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The data of the calculation of *Cirrhinus mrigala* body parts, ranges, and indices were displayed as a mean in the table below (Table 1). As indicated by many publications, slope (b) was determined to be within an acceptable range for *C. mrigala* (2.50-3.50). The slope value (b) of *C. mrigala* was discovered to be "b=2.96," which is extremely near to "3.00," representative an isometric development model. A correlation coefficient (r=0.992026) was discovered, indicating a highly substantial association between logs transformed information of total weight and length of *C. mrigala*. A total of 40 *C. mrigala* samples were collected, with sizes ranging from 23.00-51.20 cm with a mean of (39.57) in total length and 19.00-47.20 cm with a mean of (32.46) in standard length (Table 1).

Table 1: Statistical analysis i.e. Mean values, and ranges of Mori.

Body Measurements	Mean $\pm$ S.D	Range
“Wet Body weight (BW)”	641.60 $\pm$ 269.2531	125.00 - 1250.00
“Total length (TL)”	39.57 $\pm$ 1.530417	23.00 - 51.20
“Condition factor (K)”	0.97 $\pm$ 0.067659	0.80 - 1.15
“Standard length (SL)”	32.46 $\pm$ 1.929098	19.00 - 47.20
“Head length (HL)”	6.48 $\pm$ 1.106597	4.00 - 8.30
“Body girth (BG)”	19.53 $\pm$ 3.260466	11.00 - 25.00
“Dorsal fin length (DFL)”	6.83 $\pm$ 1.225415	3.70 - 8.60
“Dorsal fin base (DFB)”	6.33 $\pm$ 1.205625	2.70 - 7.90
“Pectoral fin length (PtFL)”	5.96 $\pm$ 1.37874	2.50 - 8.30
“Pectoral fin Base (PtFB)”	1.47 $\pm$ 0.500967	0.60 - 2.40
“Pelvic fin length (PvFL)”	5.23 $\pm$ 1.101046	2.90 - 8.10
“Pelvic fin base (PvFB)”	1.28 $\pm$ 0.46696	0.40 - 2.30
“Anal fin length (AFL)”	5.43 $\pm$ 0.950138	2.60 - 7.00
“Anal fin base (AFB)”	2.24 $\pm$ 0.504791	1.10 - 3.10
“Caudal fin length (CFL)”	7.11 $\pm$ 1.192057	4.00 - 9.30
“Caudal fin width (CFW)”	4.11 $\pm$ 1.271573	2.10 - 6.80

Table 1 describes the logarithmic connection of *C. mrigala* among total length and body weight (W). The coefficients of determination in the regressions were very important (r=0.992026; P0.001). Morphometric characteristics such as “standard length (SL), head length (HL), body growth (BG), dorsal fin length (DFL), dorsal fin base (DFB), pectoral fin length (PtFL), pelvic fin length (PvFL), anal fin length (AFL), anal fin base (AFB), caudal fin length (CFL), and caudal fin width (CFW)” were found to have a strong relationship with body weight as well as total length. The result value of (b) for the logarithmic relationship between “standard length” (SL) and “total length” (TL) was found (b=1.017) that is close to 1 hence shows isometric growth between TL and SL of *C. mrigala*. In length weight relationship, “SL, HL, BG, DFL, DFB, PtFL, PtFB, PvFL, PvFB, AFL, AFB, CFL and CFW” were showing negative “allometric growth” (b>1, positive allometric, b=1, isometri, b<1, negative allometric) with body weight (W) for *C. mrigala*. Condition factor (K) was observed as non-significant with both the total length and body weight of the *C. mrigala* (Table

4.14; Table 4.15). In length relationship, “SL, DFL, PvFL and AFL” were found “isometric growth” as ($b=1$) with TL for *C. mrigala*. “DFB, PvFB, PtFL, PtFB, AFB and CFW” show positive allometric growth as $b>1$, while “HL, BG, and CFL” showed negative allometric growth with TL as $b<1$ with TL in *C. mrigala*. The “Condition factor K remained insignificant” with “total length and body weight” of *C. mrigala* (Figure 2 and Figure 3).

Figure 2: LWR of *Cirrhinus mrigala* without Log.

Figure 3: Log LWR of *Cirrhinus mrigala*.

Fish Morphometry is the study of variation in shape (Webster, 2006). Fish morphology allows for the precise description of complicated structures as well as numerical comparison of diverse forms (Webster, 2006). The variance is determined by the fish's fatness, feeding intensity, or development (Froese, 2006; Rishikanta *et al.*, 2015). Differences in ecology circumstances and structure result in physical differences between geographical populations (Mirza *et al.*, 2012). The amount of scales as well as calcified tissue on the body, such “LWR” and LLR, plays a vital part in fish growth and identifying fish age (LeCren, 1951). The “LWR” and “condition factor” of a species of fish are the metrics that offer the most relevant study on growth rate and overall condition of fish, allowing the beginner to examine the condition of a fish and its population more carefully (Richter, 2007). The LWR of fish has several practical uses in fisheries and fish research. The value of condition factor (K) may be calculated on a regular basis to assist analyse the general health, physiology and productivity of the fish population (Blackwell *et al.*, 2000; Zakaria *et al.*, 2000; Bister *et al.*, 2000; Richter, 2007). Other properties of the fish are also reflected in characters (Froese, 2006).

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